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Sustainable Economic Development and Advancing Education Excellence
in the era of Global Pandemic

Editor

Khalid S. Soliman

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Ștefan Cătălin Popa, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania

Olga Makarova, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Olesya Valerievna Ivanchenko, Rostov State University of Economics, Russia
Gita Radhakrishna, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Elżbieta Rogalska, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Poland
Ciprian-Octavian Truică, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Aw Yoke Cheng, Berjaya University College, Malaysia
Jayanty Kuppusamy, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Khairunesa Isa, Universiti Tun Hussein Onn Malaysia, Malaysia
Ramona Dobre, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Ecaterina Daniela Zeca, „Dunarea de Jos” University of Galati, Romania
Honorata Howaniec, University of Bielsko-Biala, Poland
Constantin Ilie, OVIDIUS University from Constanta, Romania
Sławomir Jankiewicz, WSB University in Poznan, Poland
Maja Jokiel, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Haslinda Binti Husaini, Universiti Teknologi Mara (UiTM), Malaysia
Derweanna Bah Simpong, Universiti Malaysia Kelantan, Malaysia
Zikri Muhammad, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Olufunmilayo Tope Afolayan, Covenant University, Ota, Ogun; The Federal Polytechnic, Ilaro, Ogun State, Nigeria
Paul Ciprian Patric, Valahia University of Targoviste, Romania
Erin Olayinka, Covenant University, Nigeria
Maria Bernat, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Florin Stoica, Lucian Blaga University of Sibiu, Romania
Natalia Buchalska-Sugajska, UTP University of Science and Technology, Poland
Chuks Odiegwu-Enwerem, National Open University of Nigeria, Jabi Abuja, Nigeria
Anna Ivanova, Voronezh State University of Forestry and Technologies named after G.F. Morozov, Russia
Tomáš Sadílek, Prague University of Economics & Business, Czechia
Irina Voronova, Riga Technical University, Latvia
Stanislaw Urbanski, University of Science and Technology, Poland
Sorin Burlacu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Elena-Anca Paraschiv, National Institute for Research and Development in Informatics, Romania
Olufemi Adebayo Oladipo, Landmark University, Nigeria
Mariusz Urbański, Czestochowa UT, Poland
Hana Štverková, VŠB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Edyta Kulej-Dudek, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Ionuț Jianu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Nik Hazimah Nik Mat, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Daisy Kee Mui Hung, Universiti Sains Malaysia, Malaysia
Eva Lukášková, College of Business and Hotel Management, Czech Republic
Tatiana Borisovna Turishcheva, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Russia
Nicoleta Daniela Ignat, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Gabriela Prostean, Politehnica University of Timisoara, Romania
Ivonne Maria Gil Osorio, Universidad Libre Seccional Barranquilla, Colombia
Olga M. Kochkina, MGIMO, Russia
Adrian Moise, Petroleum-Gas University of Ploiesti, Romania
Ludmila M. Osinevich, Kursk State University, Russia
Barbara Wasilewska, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Joanna Muszyńska, Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Poland
Petrică Sorin Angheluță, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Claudiu Cicea, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Erik Ružić, Juraj Dobrila University of Pula, Croatia
Małgorzata Rataj, University of Information Technology and Management in Rzeszow, Poland
Blanka Bazsova, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Inese Lūsēna-Ezera, Liepaja University, Latvia

Tomas Broum, University of West Bohemia, Czech Republic
Dajana Barbić, Faculty of Economics & Business Zagreb, Croatia
Martina Hedvicakova, University of Hradec Králové, Czech Republic
Luis Nobre Pereira, University of Algarve, Portugal
Siti Noorsuriani Maon, Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM), Malaysia
Robert Ulewicz, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Karima Haoudi, Université Ibn Tofail, Morocco
Aleks Krasnov, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Ratna Anggraini, Jakarta State University, Indonesia
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Petr Rehacek, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Republic
Elena-Simona Apostol, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Tatiana Olegovna Dyukina, Saint-Petersburg State University, Russia
Ovidiu Blajina, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Hanane Haddad, Abdelmalik Essaâdi University, Morocco
Izabela Czabak-Górska, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Vlatka Skokic, University of Split, Croatia
Adriana Alexandru, National Institute for Resear, ICI Bucharestch and Development in Informatics, Romania
Cristiana Doina Tudor, University of Economic Studies in Bucharest, Romania
Natalia Lytneva, Oryol State University of Economics and Trade, Russia
Violetta Kuzmina, SWSU South West State University, Russia
Anna Rybak, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Katarzyna Marek-Kolodziej, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Andreea Zamfir, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Katarina Haviernikova, Alexander Dubcek University of Trencin, Slovakia
Nor Fauziana Bt Ibrahim, Multimedia University (MMU), Malaysia
Sanja Broz Tominac, University of Zgareb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Croatia
Sanja Franc, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Lawrence Uchenna Okoye, Covenant University, Ota, Nigeria
Prokopjeva Evgenia Leonidovna, Khakass Technical Institute – Branch of the Siberian Federal University, Russia
Agnieszka Knap-Stefaniuk, Jesuit University Ignatianum in Krakow, Poland
Dariusz Masłowski, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Nica Ionuț, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Elżbieta Sobczak, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Kamila Tomczak-Horyń, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Tuan Tran Hoang, University of Labour and Social Affairs (HCMC Campus), Viet Nam
Kalaiselvey Rethinam, AIMST University, Malaysia
Dorota Kwiatkowska-Ciotucha, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Rohoza Mykoła, University Poltava University of Economics and Trade, Ukraine
Vera Samarina, Staryy Oskol Technological Institute, Branch of National Research Technological University "MISIS", Russia
Jolly Sahni, Prince Sultan University, KSA
Constantin-Marius Apostoae, Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, Romania
Wojciech Bożek, University of Stettin, Poland
Mariusz Tomczyk, War Studies University, Poland
Patricio Ramirez-Correa, Uniersidad Catolica del Norte, Chile
Okorie Uchechukwu Emena, Covenant University, Nigeria
Manuela Ingaldi, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Svetlana Morkovina, Voronezh State University of Forestry and Technologies named after G.F. Morozov, Russia
Paweł Buchwald, University WSB in Dąbrowa Górnicza, Poland

Dana Kiselakova, University of Presov in Presov, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Elena Gasparovich, UrFU, Russia
Justyna Maria Myszak, University of Szczecin, Poland
Krzysztof Błoński, University of Szczecin, Poland
Petronela Cristina Simion, University "Politehnica" of Bucharest, Romania
Girjanauth Boodraj, University of Technology, Jamaica
Jakub Fučík, University of Defence, Czech Republic
Oleksandr Yukhymovych Yermakov, National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Ukraine
Alexei Dolzhenko, Rostov State University of Economics, Russia
Sylwia Konecka, Poznań University of Economics and Business, Poland
Lanre Amodu, Covenant University, Nigeria
Liliana Nicoleta Simionescu, The Bucharest University of Economics Studies, Romania
Oksana V. Haidai, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Angie O. Igbinoba, Covenant University, Nigeria
Georgiana-Raluca Lădaru, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Ruxandra Dinulescu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Piotr Kułyk, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Eugenia Czernyszewicz, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, Poland
Raisa Kozhukhivska, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
E. A. Borkova, Saint Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Katarzyna Kuziak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Ovidiu-Iulian Bunea, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Karolina Rybicka, University of Technology, Poland
Ritesh Chugh, CQUniversity, Australia
Marius Schönberger, RISEBA University of Applied Sciences, Latvia
Hezlina Mohd Hashim, Universiti Teknologi PETRONAS, Malaysia
Pedro Neves Rito, Polytechnic Institute of Viseu, Portugal
Natalia Vladimirovna Lazareva, Saint Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Krzysztof Krukowski, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn, Poland
Maja Pervan, Faculty of Economics, Business and Tourism, Croatia
Josef Botlík, Silesian University in Opava, Czechia
Beata Sofrankova, University of Presov, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Liva Grinevica, Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, Latvia
Mihai Caramihai, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Ivan Strugar, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Stefania Cristina Mirica, "Dunărea de Jos" University of Galați, Romania
Paweł Hanczar, Wroclaw University of Economics, Poland
Yong Jing Yi, INTI International College Penang, Malaysia
Edyta Zajbert, University of Economics and Business, Poland
Alena Fedorova, Ural Federal University named after the first President of Russia B.N.Yeltsin, Russia
Hind El Ouazzani, Sultan My Slimane University, Morocco
Shirley Consuelo Honajzrová Banús, Institute of Hospitality Management in Prague, Czech Republic
Alicja Malgorzata Graczyk, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Felix Sadyrbaev, Daugavpils University, Latvia
Larisa Desfontaines, St. Petersburg Peter the Great Polytechnic University, Russia
António Eduardo Martins, Universidade Aberta, Portugal
Janusz Marek Lichtarski, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Elżbieta D. Nawrocka, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Olfa Mrabet, Université Centrale - Honoris United University, Tunisia
Vladimír Bolek, University of Economics in Bratislava, Slovakia
Magdalena Swacha-Lech, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Emese Tokarčíková, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Ivica Linderová, College of Polytechnics Jihlava, Czech Republic
Eva Malichova, University of Zilina, Slovakia

Noreha Hashim, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Robert Poskart, Opole University, Poland
Tatiana Shpilina, Russian State Social University, Russia
Małgorzata Rutkowska, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Ester Piwoni-Krzeszowska, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Elizaveta Gromova, Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Alicja Brodzka, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Ayodeji Olonode, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago-Iwoye, Ogun State, Nigeria
Adrianna Guzowska, UTP University of Science and Technology in Bydgoszcz, Poland
Ekaterina Uskova, UrFU, Russia
Khatijah Omar, Universiti Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia
Ricardo Correia, Instituto Politécnico de Bragança, Portugal
Witold Kowal, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Marta Daroń, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Cezar Toader, Technical Univ. of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
Katarzyna Skrzypek, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Alfred Paszek, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Lamyaa El Bassiti, Mohammed V University in Rabat, Morocco
Razana Juhaida Johari, Universiti Teknologi MARA Shah Alam, Malaysia
Justyna Śpiewak, UTP University of Science and Technology in Bydgoszcz, Poland
Agnieszka Stanimir, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Cristina Mohora, Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania
Liviu-Adrian Cofas, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Ivani Ferreira, Instituto Federal do Paraná – IFPR, Brasil
Ivana Nekvapilova, University of Defense, Czech Republic
Funke Omole, Covenant University, Nigeria
Oleksandr Shpykuliak, National Scientific Center «Institute of Agrarian Economics», Ukraine
Miroslaw Matusek, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Iveta Linina, Turība University, Latvia
Gabriela Bucur, Petroleum Gas University of Ploiesti, Romania
Corina Marinescu, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Magdalena Kałol, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University in Lublin, Poland
Josef Dvorak, University of West Bohemia, Czech Republic
Andrey Baybarin, Southwest State University, Russia
Lina Artemenko, National Technical University of Ukraine “Igor Sikorsky Kyiv Polytechnic Institute”, Ukraine
Anna Lemańska-Majdzik, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Lorena Batagan, Bucharest University of Economics, Romania
Chiraz El Hog, Sousse University, Tunisia
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Katarzyna Grzesik, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Vladimirs Šatrevičs, Riga Technical University, Latvia
Valerii Pavliuk, Co-founder of the NGO "Association of Social Innovations and Scientific Communications", Ukraine
Tatiana Arkadyevna Karandaeva, Mari State University, Russia
Maja Pušnik, University of Maribor, Slovenia
Andreyeva Darya Andreyevna, St. Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Aurelia Vasilica Balan, University of Agricultural Sciences and Veterinary Medicine in Bucharest, Romania
Mateusz Gontarz, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Noorul Azwin Md Nasir, Uni. Malaysia Kelantan, Malaysia

Irina V. Sharf, National Research Tomsk Polytechnic University, Russia
Mária Farkasné Fekete, Institute of Economics and Methodology, Szent Istvan University, Hungary
Svetlana Kostina, Ural Federal University, Russia
Ebe Igbino, Covenant University, Nigeria
Ojebola Oluwatunmise, Covenant University, Nigeria
Malgorzata Kutera, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Agung Nugroho, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Zygmunt Kruczek, Academy of Physical Education, Faculty of Tourism and Recreation, Krakow, Poland
Tatiana Nicolaevna Larina, Orenburg State Agrarian University, Russia
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Adam Ryszko, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Katarzyna Świercz, Military University of Technology in Warsaw, Poland
Anna Kobińska, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, Poland
James Braman, Community College of Baltimore County, USA
Dragan Benazic, Juraj Dobrila University of Pula, Croatia
Sergei Smirnov, St-Petersburg State University, Russia
Zuliani Dalimunthe, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Dorota Domalewska, War Studies University, Poland
Viktorija Špilova, Daugavpils University, Latvia
Arshad Ahmad, King Saud University, KSA
Imen Chaouachi Allani, University of Carthage, Tunisia
Mukhamediyev B.M., Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan
Agnieszka Szczudlińska-Kanoś, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Arkadiusz Piwowar, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Zied Akrou, University of Sfax, Tunisia
Cecilia Cristina Socorro Gonzalez, Universidad del Zulia, Venezuela
Damir Kalpić, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Mirosław Moroz, Wrocław University of Economics, Poland
Katarzyna Łukasik, Częstochowa University of Technology, Poland
Taiye Tairat Borishade, Covenant University, Nigeria
Olena Reshetnyak, Research Centre for Industrial Problems of Development of the National Academy of Sciences, Ukraine
Jana Mitříková, University of Prešov, Slovakia
Dorin Maier, Technical University of Cluj-Napoca, Romania
Alexander Obydenov, Financial University, Russia
Jan Strohmandl, Tomas Bata University in Zlín, Czech Republic
Ruslan Bazhenov, Sholom-Alechem Priamursky State University, Russia
Justyna Zygmunt, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Andreea-Florina Fora, University of Oradea, Romania
Amal Trifa, National School of Computer Sciences, Tunisia
Agnieszka Komor, University of Life Sciences in Lublin, Poland
Arkadiusz Kowalski, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Nasrine Shah Abushakra, Esol Education, UAE
Ilona Bondos, Maria Curie-Skłodowska University, Poland
Anna Wziętek-Staśko, Jagiellonian University in Kraków, Faculty of Management and Social Communication, Poland
Alexandra Baicoianu, Transilvania University of Brasov, Romania
Joanna Antczak, War Studies University, Warsaw, Poland
Larisa Yu. Ovsyanitskaya, International Institute of Design and Service, Russia
Sunita Lylia Hamdan, Multimedia University, Malaysia
Andrzej Skibiński, Częstochowa University of Technology, Poland
Henry C. Nweke-Love, Landmark University, Nigeria
Anna Saniuk, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Ivana Bilić, University of Split, Faculty of Economics, Business and Tourism, Croatia

Oses Isibor, Lagos City Polytechnic, Ikeja, Nigeria
Konstantin Shvetsov, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University (SPbPU), Russia
Tamara Selishcheva, Saint Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Felipe Machorro Ramos, Universidad de las Américas Puebla, México
Fitra Lestari, UIN Sultan Syarif Kasim, Indonesia
Iwona Pisz, The University of Opole, Opole
Ismi Rajiani, Lambung Mangkurat, Indonesia
Tamara V. Talanova, Chuvash State University, Russia
Ilham El Haraoui, Ibn Tofail University, Morocco
Miłosz Gac, WSB University in Gdańsk, Poland
Teresa Proença, University of Porto, Faculty of Economics, Portugal
Patrycja Kokot-Stępień, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Alexandra Cristina Dinu, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Mariam Mateen Khan, Institute of Business Management (IoBM), Pakistan
Elena V. Butsenko, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
Anna Chechel, Donetsk State University of Management, Ukraine
Feyza Ağlargoöz, Anadolu University, Turkey
Ireneusz Miciuła, University of Szczecin
Olga Bucovetchi, University Politehnica of Bucharest, Romania
Anna Sylwia Kowalska, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Anna Mayakova, SWSU, Russia
Ataina Hudayati, Universitas Islam Indonesia, Indonesia
Sebastian Saniuk, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Marek Szajt, Technical University of Częstochowa, Poland
Isaiah O. Olurinola, Covenant University, Nigeria
Christian Enz, University of South Bohemia, Czech Republic
Aida Matri Ben Jemaa, High Institute of Management (Tunis), Tunisia
Dan Dumitriu, POLITEHNICA University of Bucharest, Romania
Anna Mempel-Śnieżyk, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Daniela Zirra, Romanian-American University, Romania
Nataliia Orlova, Professional Development Center of Kiev Region, Ukraine
Marta Nowak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Lucie Severová, Czech University of Agriculture, Czech Republic
Elena Iadrennikova, Ural Federal University named after the first President of Russia B.N. Yeltsin (UrFU), Russia
Maria Plakhotnikova, Financial University under the Government of the Russian Federation, Russia
Elena Lysenko, UrFU, Russia
Anetta Barska, University of Zielona Góra, Poland
Ika Permatasari, Universitas Negeri Surabaya, Indonesia
Lukáš Smerek, Matej Bel University in Banská Bystrica, Slovakia
Alicja Sekuła, Gdansk University of Technology, Poland
Magdalena Sobocińska, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Anita Peša, University of Zadar, Croatia
Francisco Andrés García Barrera, Universidad Arturo Prat, Chile
Liudmyla Melnyk, Uman National University of Horticulture, Ukraine
Marcin Lawnik, Silesian University of Technology, Poland
Małgorzata Macuda, Uniwersytet Ekonomiczny w Poznaniu, Poland
Janusz Wielki, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Viktoria Anatolievna Degtereva, Peter the Great St. Petersburg Polytechnic University, Russia
Monika Hadaś-Dyduch, University of Economy in Katowice, Poland
Intan Salwani Mohamed, Universiti Teknologi MARA, Malaysia
Sandeep Kumar, Tecnia Institute of Advanced Studies, Affiliated to GGSIP University, New Delhi, India
Marta Starostka-Patyk, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Martha Rodríguez-Villalobos, Universidad de Monterrey, México
Cristian Mera Macías, Universidad Laica Eloy Alfaro de Manabí, Ecuador

Klaudia Przybysz, Wrocław University of Economics & Business, Poland
Jarosław Górecki, UTP University of Science and Technology, Poland
Valery Maslennikov, Plekhanov Russian Economic University, Russia
Nibedita Saha, Tomas Bata University in Zlin, University Institute, Czech Republic
Katarína Rentková, Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Mohammad Kamal Kamel Afaneh, Al Imam Mohammad Ibn Saud Islamic University (IMSIU), KSA
Basel M. Al-Eideh, Kuwait University, Kuwait
Blanka Tundys, University of Szczecin, Poland
Daniela Matušiková, University of Prešov in Prešov, Slovakia
Patrick Omoruyi Eke, Lagos State University, Nigeria
Muntazir Haider Ali, Institute of Business Management, Karachi
Magdalena M. Stuss, Jagiellonian University, Poland
Adebanji W. Ayeni, Landmark University, Nigeria
Monika Kozerska, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Ines Ben Messaoud, University of Gabes / University of Sfax, Tunisia
Konstantin B. Kostin, UNECON, Russia
Oscar Odiboh, Covenant University, Nigeria
Sebastian Kot, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Alla Ivashchenko, Kyiv National Economic University named after Vadim Hetman, Ukraine
Ivana Barišić, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Croatia
Lubov Afanasjeva, Southwest State University, Kursk, Russia
Alexander Grebenkov, Southwest State University, Russia
Anastasiya Kopytova, Tomsk State Pedagogical University, Russia
Ganna Likhonosova, National Aerospace University «Kharkiv Aviation Institute», Ukraine
Małgorzata Pańkowska, University of Economics in Katowice, Poland
Dyah Setyaningrum, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Maja Mihelja Žaja, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Justyna Dobroszek, University of Lodz, Poland
Besma Hkiri, Jeddah University, KSA
Irina V. Kokushkina, Saint Petersburg State University, Russia
Elena Vasilyeva, Moscow State University of Civil Engineering, Russia
Anastasiya Peshka, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
IseOlorunkanmi OjO Joseph, Landmark University, Nigeria
Mohammed Adnan Moreb, Altinbas University, Turkey
Fred O. Peter, Covenant University, Nigeria
Boris Tušek, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Economics and Business, Croatia
Katarzyna Tworek, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Poland
Ivana Bulog, Faculty of Economics, Business and Tourism, University of Split, Croatia
Nina Golowko, Self-employed Lecturer, Germany
Olga Ivanovna Solodukhina, Southwest State University, Russia
Galina Bannykh, Ural Federal University, Russia
Joanna WYROBEK, Cracow University of Economics, Poland
Agnieszka Małkowska, University of Szczecin, Poland
Ingrid Majerova, Silesian University in Opava, Czech Republic
Andra-Elena Diaconescu, Politehnica University Timisoara, Romania
Lukas Valek, University of Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic
Boris Miethlich, Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of Management, Slovakia
Nataša Šarlija, University of Osijek, Croatia
Stéphane Bourliataux-Lajoinie, CNAM Paris, France
Yuliya Karpovich, Perm National Research Polytechnic University, Russia
Daria Elżbieta Jaremen, Wrocław University of Economics and Business, Poland
Sabina Kubiciel-Lodzińska, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Agboola Mayowa Gbenga, Covenant University, Nigeria
Agnieszka Dobrowolska, Institute of Meteorology and Water Management – National Research Institute, Poland

Fjodor Ruzic, Institute for Informatics, Croatia
Victoria Viaznikova, Mari State University, Russia
Mohammad Falahat, UTAR, Malaysia
Radoslav Jankal, University of Zilina, Slovakia
Natalia Vladimirovna Sharapova, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
Gennadiy Sheptalin, South Ural State University, Russia
Valentina Mikhailovna Sharapova, Ural State University of Economics, Russia
Renata Brajer-Marczak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Anastasia Ilyina, Kyiv National University of Trade and Economics, Ukraine
Tijani Amara, University of Gafsa, Tunisia
Tatyana Golovina, Central Russian Institute of Management, Branch of RANEP, Russia
Olena Berezina, Cherkasy State Technological University, Ukraine
Victoria B. Malitskaya, Plekhanov Russian University of Economics, Russia
Agnieszka Bieńkowska, Wroclaw University of Sciences and Technology, Poland
S. Jumambayev, Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Kazakhstan
Jarosław Olejniczak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business
Djula Borozan, Josip Juraj Strossmayer University of Osijek, Faculty of Economics in Osijek, Croatia
Nawaz Mohamudally, University of Technology, Mauritius, Mauritius
Piotr Bolibok, The John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, Poland
Cătălina Florentina Albu, The Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Patrycja Zwiech, University of Szczecin, Poland
Monika Sipa, Czestochowa University of Technology, Poland
Elena Nebolsina, MGIMO University, Russia
Dorota Bednarska-Olejniczak, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Jolanta Maj, Opole University of Technology, Poland
Natalya Sopilko, Russian State Social University, Russia
Elena Davydenko, St. Petersburg State University, Russia
Laurentiu Gabriel Talaghir, Dunarea de Jos University of Galati, Romania
Maria Federica Cordova, UNISA, Italy
Souhir Amri Amamou, University of Tunis, Tunisia
Irina N. Rogova, St-Petersburg State University of Economics, Russia
Bodislav Dumitru Alexandru, Bucharest University of Economic Studies, Romania
Eva W.L. Lim, UCSI University, Malaysia
Anetta Pukas, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business, Poland
Siti Nuryanah, Universitas Indonesia, Indonesia
Vladimir Nosov, K.G. Razumovsky Moscow State University of technologies and management; Academy of the Investigative Committee of the Russian Federation, Russia
Svitlana Naumenkova, Taras Shevchenko National University of Kyiv, Ukraine
Boris Mucha, Comenius University in Bratislava, Faculty of management, Slovakia
Athanasios Podaras, Technical University of Liberec, Czech Republic
Galina Yu. Fedotova, The Russian Presidential Academy of National Economy and Public Administration, Russia
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Potential Management of The Enterprise from The Position of Functional Approach

KNIAZ SVIATOSLAV

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 E-mail: svkniaz@ukr.net

HEORHIADI NELLI

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 E-mail: nelli.heorhiadi@gmail.com

SAI LESIA

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 E-mail: sayko.say2017@gmail.com

SHCHEBEL ANDRII

Lviv University of Business and Law, Lviv, Ukraine, 79021 E-mail: peet_@ukr.net

MOROZ SVITLANA

Poltava State Agrarian Academy, Poltava, Ukraine, 36003 E-mail: smor@meta.ua

KALASHNYK OLENA

Poltava State Agrarian Academy, Poltava, Ukraine, 36003 E-mail: kalashnik1968@meta.ua

SPITSYNA ANHELINA

National Transport University, Kyiv, Ukraine, 02000 E-mail: angel7a@ukr.net

KYRYCHENKO OLENA

Higher Educational Establishment of Ukoopspilka "Poltava University of Economics and Trade", Poltava, Ukraine, 36000 E-mail: olena.kyrychenko2010@gmail.com

VILHUTSKA ROKSOLANA

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 E-mail: roksoliana.b.vilhutska@lpnu.ua

PEREDALO KHRYSTYNA

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 E-mail: khrystyna.s.peredalo@lpnu.ua

MYSKIV IRYNA

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 Email: myskiviryna@i.ua

SHAYNER HANNA

Lviv Polytechnic National University, Lviv, Ukraine, 79013 Email: ann.shayner@gmail.com

Annotation

The potential of the enterprise is considered as a system of opportunities to achieve development goals within the functions defined by the structure of the enterprise. In turn, the management of the enterprise potential is disclosed as a specific function of management. It is proved that it is based on a specific object of management - of the enterprise potential. It is substantiated that the management of this object is carried out by the heads of the enterprise using management methods and technologies, the selection and application of which is carried out within the general management functions (planning, organizing, motivating, controlling and regulating). Since the potential of the enterprise is a complex object of management, which includes production, marketing, investment and other potentials, there is a reason to believe that the goals of managing the potential of the enterprise is a

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complex, hierarchical system. Their implementation requires constant monitoring and regulation of the object of management.

Keywords: Enterprise, Potential, Management System, Functional Approach, Management Goals.

Introduction

The development of any business depends on its potential. At the same time, it should be recognized that regardless of the type of activity of enterprises, their form of ownership, as well as size, there are certain components of the potential of enterprises that are common to all businesses, and there are those that are specific to specific enterprises. Strictly speaking, this difference in potentials largely determines the vectors and intensity of enterprise development, their competitiveness and investment attractiveness. Nevertheless, it is known that among the total number of enterprises there are those that have a significant potential, but its implementation is low. This situation and the reasons for this may be due to both objective and subjective factors, in particular - irrational capacity management, underdeveloped system of organizational development, lack of signs of innovation in solving problems of management and engineering technology. The problem is not systematic and fragmentary theoretical and methodological and applied provisions for managing the potential of the enterprise in the coordinate system of organizational development.

Literature Review

Exploring the potential of enterprises, most economists focus on determining its essence and structure (Bykova N.V., 2011), (Rovenska V.V., 2012), (Piliavskiy V.I., 2019) problems of capacity formation and use, (Zbrodska O.V., 2011), (Hnatieva T. and Livinskii A., 2019), (Garayev M., 2019), (Shabatura T., 2019), (Dergachova V., Ovcharova S., & Martynenk, O., 2019) its evaluation (Kviatkovska L.A., 2011), (Boykivska G.M., 2011), (Zadneprovska G.I., 2015), (Burachek I., & Pravda O., 2015), (Dogadaylo Ya., 2017), (Vasylyk N.M., 2018), (Piletska S.T., Korytko T.Yu. 2018), (Azhaman I. A., Zhydko O.I., 2019), (Samorodov B.V., Saukh I.V., Vygovska N.G., 2019), (Sydorova A., & Hontjuk V., 2019)) and management (Shot A.P., 2009), (Durbalova N., Sedikova I., 2019) . Among these scientific works are those that are devoted to the study of the potential of the enterprise as a whole (Rovenska V.V., 2012), (Dogadaylo Ya., 2017), (Garayev M., 2019), as well as works in which such types of potentials, such as: anti-crisis (Piletska S.T., Korytko T.Yu. 2018), innovative (Zadneprovska G.I., 2015), (Piliavskiy V.I., 2019), competitive (Durbalova N., Sedikova I., 2019), economic (Azhaman I.A., Zhydkov O.I., 2019), (Shabatura T., 2019), investment (Garayev M., 2019), resource (Zbrodska O.V., 2011), (Vasylyk N.M., 2018), financial (Samorodov B.V., Saukh I.V., Vygovska N.G., 2019), personnel (Shovkun L.V. , 2010), (Burachek I., & Pravda O., 2015), (Sydorova A., & Hontjuk V., 2019) and export (Stakhorskiy O.O., 2010), (Bykova N.V., 2011), (Dergachova V., Ovcharova S., & Martynenko, O., 2019). Based on the polyvector studies of the enterprise potential, we can say that their systematization and coordination with each other is quite uncertain. This highlights the problem of clarifying the essential characteristics and types of the enterprise potential.

The scientific literature considers both general aspects of the management process (planning, analysis, control, assessment of the level of use of components) and the model of enterprise potential management in particular (organization, evaluation, diagnosis, search for sources and reserves of components of enterprise potential) (Knyaz S., 2020). Thus, Luchkova M. considers the management of strategic potential and determines its following structure: determining the current level of use of strategic potential, assessing the level of use of strategic potential, making and implementing appropriate decisions on strategic potential management; control over the use of the strategic potential of the enterprise (Luchkova M.S., 2011). Vasylykivskiy D. examines the management of marketing potential of the enterprise and notes the sequence of actions: definition and formation of the structure of potential; analysis of competitive advantages and capabilities of the enterprise; identifying the interaction of each element of potential; integrated assessment of the competitiveness of the enterprise (Vasylykivskiy D.M., 2011). Otenko I. notes that the management of the economic potential of the enterprise is both current and strategic. Applying a functional approach, the author has formed a mechanism for managing the economic potential of the enterprise, the main functions of which are,"coordination; assessment and analysis; planned; motivation that promotes the activation of the processes of self-development of employees of the enterprise and the maximum return of creative and innovative potential of management staff and management; organization; monitoring and technological control (previous, guiding, subsequent); marketing "(Otenko I.P., 2015). Authors Vasylyeva T.A.,

Leono, S.V., Kryvych Y.M. researching management of innovative potential note that the management process itself is, "... a systematic, dynamic, planned and complex activity to ensure the strategic viability of the enterprise by finding creative ideas for introduction of new goods and services, as well as methods of their promotion through continuous improvement of technology, increasing competitiveness... "and describe the very sequence of the management system, highlighting the relevant stages: goal setting, diagnosis of innovation potential, development strategy for further development, monitoring and evaluation of results Vasylieva T.A., Leonov S.V., Kryvych J.M., 2011). Research on the formation and management of competitive potential was carried out by Petrovych J. and Lushchak N., who determined that the management of competitive potential is a complex process that must constantly change under the influence of innovative development of society and economy, but it must be provided with innovative content to improve product quality, optimization of technological processes, improving the organization of sales activities (Petrovych J., Lushchak N., 2011). Bozhanova O. researching theoretical approaches to managing the economic potential of the enterprise, substantiates the feasibility of using modern management concepts, including the interaction of systemic and situational approaches. Also, the author argues that the management of economic potential should be implemented through the implementation of specific and certain functions depending on the sectoral characteristics of enterprises, their size, organizational forms of activity (Bozhanova O., 2010). Tolpezhnikov R. proposed an organizational and economic mechanism of adapted management of the potential of an industrial enterprise, which is formed from a set of interdependent elements of internal potential (control unit and resource block) and micropotential (financial potential - financial and credit potential - market value) and adapted to external environment. Based on the functional approach, the author substantiates that the interaction of these components can provide a positive strategic effect (Tolpezhnikov R., 2012). Grabchuk O. and Bovsunovska G. formed a general scheme of enterprise potential management, which includes eight stages: formation of information base on potential management, analysis and selection of priorities from the enterprise mission in the formation of management strategy, evaluation of financial results, evaluation of enterprise potential, system definition relationships between financial results and enterprise potential, development of enterprise potential management strategy, implementation of enterprise potential management strategy using selected methods and tools, analysis and control of management strategy (Grabchuk O. and Bovsunovska G., 2016). Rzayev G. investigating the problematic issues of management, related to ensuring the effective use of enterprise potential, justifies the need for systematic monitoring of the level of enterprise potential, which will track changes in key external and internal factors, analyze performance, make adjustments to the management system potential of the enterprise (Rzayev G., 2014). Zakharenko M. the organizational and economic bases of formation of system of management of potential of the enterprise are considered, characteristic features of its elements which need to be considered at formation of potential and its further effective use are defined. The author highlighted in the management system of production potential of the subsystem: target; providing; managed and managing (Zakharenko M., 2018). Shandrivska O., Kuziak V. and Beck O. researching the approaches to management of enterprise potential and its strategic development described in scientific works, define it as "... process of acceptance and realization of the administrative decisions directed on an estimation and realization of possibilities of improvement of the enterprise potential, setting new value and ensuring the strategic development of the enterprise "and form an appropriate model for managing the strategic development of the enterprise, which contains such key elements as: formulating the mission of the enterprise, setting goals, forming a strategy for enterprise development, comprehensive analysis of enterprise potential (state and development, efficiency and formation), the formation of the optimal structure of potential on the basis of synergistic interaction of its components in accordance with the strategic goals of the enterprise, the choice of the most effective alternative to enterprise development, the formation of enterprise development strategy (Shandrivska O., Kuziak V. and Beck O., 2013). Gonchar O. studied the functional and organizational aspects of enterprise potential management on the basis of synergy and determined that the formation and improvement of enterprise potential are determined by the strength of the relationship and interaction of its elements, and taking into account the synergistic effect of enterprise potential elements will allow gaining competitive advantages, combinations of resources, increasing the value of the enterprise as a set of tangible and intangible assets, increasing the resilience of the economic system to uncertainties and risks that arise in the process of evolution "(Gonchar O., 2015).

Thus, in the theory and practice of modern management functional approach is quite popular.

Purpose of Research

The purpose of the article is to distinguish the stages of managing the formation of enterprise potential from the standpoint of a functional approach. To achieve this goal it is necessary: to clarify the essence of the concept of

"enterprise potential"; to reveal the essence of enterprise potential management from the standpoint of a functional approach.

Research results. The application of a functional approach is a necessary but insufficient condition for clarifying the essence of the concept of "enterprise potential". Thus, functions can be considered from the standpoint of management, production, technology and more. Given this, in addition to functional, it is advisable to use a structural-system approach.

Let's clarify the basic functional and structural characteristics that are relevant for any enterprise, as well as derivative functional and structural characteristics of enterprises (Table 1).

Table 1: Functional and structural characteristics of the enterprise

Features	Structures	Functions
Basic		
Management	Management system	Planning; organization; motivation; control; regulation
Production and technological	Production and technological system	- Procurement or creation of resources; - production; - sales
Derivatives		
Marketing	Marketing and advertising system	- Marketing and advertising management; - conducting marketing research and advertising campaigns
Logistics	Logistics system	- Resource flow management; - development of logistics structure
Innovative	The system of innovative activity of the enterprise	- Innovation management; - development and implementation of innovations
.....
Information	Information support system	Information support management; - collection, processing, storage and use of information; - providing managers and subordinates of the enterprise with technical means and software products for the collection, processing, storage and use of information; - establishment of communications

On the basis of basic and derivative functionally structural characteristics of the enterprise it is possible to allocate and construct classification of potentials of the enterprise on a number of signs, namely:

by its content:

- management, production, marketing, logistics, innovation, information, etc. (these are the potentials of the enterprise to implement certain functions). Enterprises that work in the market for a long time usually have a developed structure. Each structural component of the enterprise implements one or more functions. To perform these functions in the structure of the enterprise they form the appropriate staff, develop strategies and tactics to achieve the goals set for employees, develop certain rules and procedures of subordination, formalize methods and technologies of functional implementation of this structural component. In turn, the functional and structural characteristics of newly established enterprises are quite limited. Often such enterprises have the most simplified structure, in which there are no structural components, but rather a functional division of responsibilities between employees for certain sectors of activity. Under such conditions, enterprises, for the most part, have only managerial and production potential);

by nature:

- basic (managerial and production) and derivative (all other potentials) potentials. Basic potentials are characteristic of all enterprises without exception, their presence is a condition for the functioning of any enterprise. As for the derivative potentials, they are typical for enterprises with developed management systems and production and technological systems;

according to the level of development of the functional structure of the enterprise:

- developed (high or low) potential (high potential occurs when the company owns and successfully uses a certain functional structure. In turn, in conditions when a certain functional structure exists but is poorly implemented, then there is a low potential);

- undeveloped (zero) potential (this type of potential occurs when the company does not implement a certain function and there is no appropriate structure for this).

Thus, the potential of the enterprise should be considered as a system of opportunities to achieve development goals within the functions defined by the structure of the enterprise. It should be recognized that the structure of the enterprise may be more or less developed, for example, despite the fact that any enterprise accumulates, stores, processes and uses information for engineering and technological and management decisions, but not all enterprises have an information system. The same applies to logistics systems, marketing and advertising, security, innovation, and so on. Based on this, there is a reason to believe that the level of potential of the enterprise depends on the level of development of the functional structure of the enterprise. If the information support system is not developed, then the information support function is underdeveloped, and this is evidence of the low level of information support potential of the enterprise. Further research should be conducted in the direction of building a structural and functional model for identifying the competitive advantages of enterprises, taking into account the identified features of the potential of enterprises.

Based on the generalization of the above literature sources, there is a reason to believe that in the scientific literature at the enterprise level management is considered as an open system, the characteristics of which depend on the size of the enterprise, its level of diversification and market share, innovation, professionalism of managers, etc. Regardless of the specifics of building a management system, it performs general and specific functions under any circumstances. There are some differences among management theorists regarding the list of these functions, but in general, among the general functions are such as: planning, organizing, motivating, controlling and regulating. As for specific functions, their list is much larger, because these functions are based on specific objects of management, such as production activities of the enterprise, supply, sales, investment activities, marketing, innovation, as well as various types of potential - production, technology, intellectual, personnel, innovation, investment, etc. In view of this, the specific functions of the enterprise management system include production management, supply management, sales management, investment management, marketing management, innovation management, production capacity management, technological capacity management, intellectual capacity management, human resources management, management of innovation potential, management of investment potential, etc. Fig. 1. shows the place of the potential of the enterprise as a specific function in the management system of the enterprise.

Fig. 1: The place of enterprise potential in the enterprise management system

As you can see, the subjects of management, namely managers, defining the mission, vision and building goals of enterprise development (enterprise development goals, or system of enterprise goals is a hierarchically and functionally ordered set of mutually agreed tasks, as have clear deadlines and criteria). Traditionally, the system of enterprise goals distinguishes three hierarchical levels - strategic, tactical and operational at each of which are formed and implemented, respectively, strategic, tactical and operational plans for enterprise development. The key conditions for ensuring the effectiveness of enterprise goals are their realism, relevance and consistency) managing the potential of the enterprise through its planning, organization, motivation, control and regulation.

In the context of these general functions there is the use of management methods and technologies, the application of which is aimed at the object of management - the enterprise potential

Given that the company may be at the stage of formation or development, its potential may be formed or undergo changes that lead to its loss, reproduction or growth (increase). In fig. 2 it is shown a fragment of the causal-structural model of the formation of the enterprise potential, which is in its state of formation.

Fig. 2: A fragment of the causal-structural model of forming the potential of the enterprise from the standpoint of a functional approach

At the stage of the enterprise formation of its potential it is accompanied by a number of successive stages of management, namely: definition of the purposes of formation of the enterprise potential taking into account factors of internal and external environment of the enterprise; organizing activities to build the potential of the enterprise; motivating employees to implement the set tasks within the measures defined at the previous stage; controlling the process of forming of the enterprise potential; regulation of the process of forming of the enterprise potential (Fedulova I., 2009).

Each of these stages is aimed at structural modeling of enterprise potential. Thus, Fig. 2 considers the formation of the enterprise potential on the example of its components such as production potential. Deciding on the formation of this component of the potential of the enterprise requires market research, assessing the capabilities of the enterprise and on the basis of this formation of strategic production goals of the enterprise (Knyaz S., 2015). Based on these goals, it is possible to determine the required amount of production capacity, area, raw materials, materials, etc. This information is necessary to create the material and technical conditions for the production activities of the enterprise. Having created them actually there is a production potential which can be used for realization of the established strategic purposes.

At the stage of realization of production potential the management system of the enterprise is directed on control and regulation of processes of use of production capacities, areas, resources, etc. taking into account change of factors of internal and, especially, external environments for timely acceptance and realization of corrective administrative decisions. (Georgiadi N. and others, 2020).

In conditions when the enterprise functions in the market for a long time, that is at a stage of the development the task of heads of the enterprise is so to carry out management of its potential from which it was reproduced and grew. In fig. 3 it is shown options for increasing the potential of the enterprise. In this case, the reproduction of potential means the restoration of the company's ability to implement those tasks that were performed in the past, in particular to produce the same as in the past, the volume of products, occupy the same market share, perform previously committed, etc.

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Conclusions

Under the potential of the enterprise should be understood as a system of opportunities to achieve development goals within the functions defined by the structure of the enterprise. Management of enterprise potential is a specific function of management, which is implemented on the basis of management methods and technologies, the selection and application of which is carried out within the general management functions. From the standpoint of functional-structural approach, the classification of enterprise potentials is specified, in particular, classification features and types of potentials (in terms of content - management, production, marketing, logistics, innovation, information, etc. ; by nature - basic (management and production) and derivatives (marketing, logistics, innovation, information, etc.) potentials, according to the level of development of the functional structure - developed (high, low) and undeveloped (zero) potentials).

It is substantiated that at the enterprise level modeling of its potential should have a causal-structural character, where the objects of functional-process management are the goals of capacity formation (market sector share, level of competitiveness, etc.), internal factors of the enterprise that characterize the enterprise potential (market sector share, areas of production capacity, stocks of raw materials, number of workers, etc.), as well as types of potential (production, technological, sales, marketing, etc.). It is substantiated that such objects should be focused on such management processes as: a) definition of the purposes of formation of potential of the enterprise taking into account factors of internal and external environment of the enterprise; b) organizing activities to build the potential of the enterprise; c) motivating employees to implement the set tasks within the measures defined at the previous stage; d) controlling the process of forming the potential of the enterprise; e) regulation of the process of forming the potential of the enterprise. It is under the conditions of forming the potential of the enterprise on the basis of the causal-structural model that it is possible to achieve rationality in the management of the enterprise potential.

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